

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ODIGIE****FIRST NAME: JOSEPH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

ACA-401/ACA401D COURSEPACK PEROD1 RP

1) INTRODUCTION

Policy and decision-makers all over the world desire to have evidence-based, logical, and useful information from academic essay writers for individual, cooperate, and national development. An excellent academic essay follows an argument and a clear structural form. In this response paper, I will discuss academic essay writing, analyze, and give the present and future implications of writing an internationally acceptable essay.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Researchers across the globe are always seeking the best possible ways to convince readers to understand and accept the idea they have about emerging issues through evidence.” An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). This further buttresses the importance of writing and conveying a view through a well-structured and consistent style of writing. Beginning an essay, therefore, requires well thought out steps.

i. Designing an essay

The process of writing an essay demands a coordinated starting point. At the commencement of an article, the researcher will have to first “define the question and analyze the task and *diligently* construct an initial plan as a roadmap. Also, that writers understand precisely what the question requires by identifying the key words likes to discuss or analyze. An essay plan can help structure as well as work out how to answer

the question and which information to use” (EUCLID 2019, 1). The above view, for me, should be taken as the firm foundation upon which I can achieve a quality essay. An essay plan, therefore, should include reading the work of other researchers for inspiration and drive.

ii. *Researching other writers’ essay*

A successful essay also requires knowledge and evidence that helps to build up arguments and answer to the research question. Through studying the works of other researchers in the subject area, I can develop experience, evidence, reasoning, and answers for the essay question—my vital lesson from the EUCLID Course ACA-401D Period 1 material on essay writing. However, writers can misapply knowledge and evidence not adequately organized.

iii. *Organizing note taken during research*

The proper organization of notes taken from reading and researching the works of other researchers will ultimately bring about answers to the essay question. Given this, a *well-developed and organized ideal will help in the presentation of arguments and logical flow of point of view put forward*. The aggregation of ideas can create a broad perspective while, in turn, narrowing it to a focal point before the essay writing can begin.

iv. *Beginning the essay*

The actual writing of an essay starts and ends with the structure and framework. The EUCLID Course Material ACA-401D concisely explained this as introduction, body, and conclusion. I have gained tremendous knowledge and a better understanding of academic essay writing in this section. Appropriate referencing and quality editing of such work will further make it more attractive to readers and other researchers.

v. *Selecting the reference style*

Deciding on the style of reference is directly related to the subject area. “All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offense” (EUCLID 2019, 4). Citation of references gives a positive impression of the writer. Demonstrates compliance with copyright regulations as well as an understanding of what plagiarism is all about. One way to avoid this crime is to edit the essay as many times as possible before for publication.

vi. *Editing*

Editing can be viewed as the careful cross-checking of a written piece of work and ensuring strict adherence to all standards of writing and publications. This section of the course material taught me more lessons about the need for error-free work and double-checking, which is the precursor of a quality essay before submission.

vii. *Handing in the essay*

Turning in an academic essay can be seen as the finishing line. “You have not completed your assignment until you have handed it in” (EUCLID 2019, 4). It follows, therefore, that it must be devoid of plagiarism. Based on this, an essay submitted marks the end of it.

viii. *Understanding plagiarism*

Plagiarism means copying, quoting, paraphrasing, or pasting the work of an author by writers without acknowledging the source. “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). I have also found this chapter of the course a beneficial tool to have in this program. Citation, paraphrasing, quotation, logical, and footnote styles were of great importance and benefit to me. In order to avoid academic sanctions, therefore, all researchers need to follow rules of thumb for paper writing.

ix. *Applying the rule of thumb*

Rules help to coordinate, organize, and create consistency or pattern in writing. Chapter three of the course mentioned some jurisdictions, such as stating the central thesis, staying focused, clear writing, supporting, and assertion, among others. The point above is instructive and informative for a program of this nature. The Chicago Rules (Turabian) recommended by EUCLID came to me as a clear and straightforward style to adopt in the complexities and differences between American and British English.

x. *The use of American and British English*

Though American and British English featured interchangeably, the similarity or otherwise difference calls for the use of one for consistency and readers benefit. I found the section compelling to avoid the application of both Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English in essay writing. For example, while American writes the date as “Month Day Year, British English is Day Month Year” (EUCLID 2019, 48). Consequently, adopting the two styles in the same essay will result in inconsistency in our work. So, it is imperative to ensure that the Chicago Manual of Style recommended by EUCLID is applied to achieve our desired result.

xi. *The Chicago manual of style*

An excellent academic essay is a function of various inputs, style, and usage of standard. The Chicago Style and its usage, as explained in the section, was a well-structured and precise piece of work by the author. The illustrations on the use of abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, emphases (italic and quotes), numbering, and dates, as well as quotations, made my understanding an easy one. For this reason, I found it seamless in its application for this response paper. However, a good knowledge of the Chicago page formatting style is a need to make our work even better.

a) Chicago page formatting

Formatting is the process of aligning an essay to an acceptable and readable style in writing and publication. Ensuring that margin, fonts, indents, paper type, justification, spacing, and page number conforms to the recommended standard create a scholarly impression about the writer. Hence, using Chicago formatting in every aspect of writing, including endnotes and footnotes, generally makes our paper attractive to our target population.

i) *Chicago endnote and footnotes*

Writers at one stage or the other will have to research the work of other researchers in search of evidence and illustrations to support or rejects the argument or point of view put forward. To accept or discard the idea of the writer, scholars, and readers usually examine the evidence presented by the author. Therefore, it is now imperative to adopt in our writing the Standard Endnote and Footnotes format when citing books, journals and newspapers, reports, and papers, reports, and references as well as other sources and documents. This section of the course material is one indispensable knowledge I have benefitted and put to use as I write this paper. Similarly, technical communicators and others who apply Latin abbreviations and expressions in their writing will find the appropriate use of endnotes and footnote crucial.

ii) *Latin abbreviation and expression*

Though Latin abbreviations and terms have found a central place in referencing, its correct application must be with proper understanding and clarity. “Latin abbreviation is appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (for example, the information in parenthesis). Business, formal, and technical writing uses the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by the reader” (EUCLID 2019, 56). In this regard, its application is necessary and also avoids the use of it with a suitable alternative in plain English.

3) CONCLUSION

Academic essay writing requires, among other necessary skills, knowledge, and comprehension. However, the EUCLID course material had neither in-text referencing nor superscript numbering in the body of the text. Nevertheless, the quality and unique piece of work is full of fresh insight and direction to enable the development of a successful and internationally acceptable essay. Since all chapters were simple and clear with no controversial and misleading explanation, I received new knowledge and understanding of the subject matter beyond my expectations that will continue to be helpful at this moment and in the future. This material will forever meet the writers’ desired impact on all readers in the present and years to come as it undergoes reviews to conform to prevailing realities, updates, and findings. Also, this will breed new corps of scholars, award-winning authors,

speakers, Chief Executive Officers (CEOs), and multi-disciplinary researchers and development experts, as well as produce reliable, balanced, and productive solutions to global challenges.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed, 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.